

Tapis Systems Enable Collaborative Data Management in Science Gateways

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Abstract—Science gateways connect researchers to high-performance computing (HPC) resources by providing a graphical interface to manage data and submit jobs. Scientific research is a highly collaborative activity, and gateways can play an important role by providing shared data management tools that reduce the need for advanced expertise in file system administration. We describe a recently implemented architecture for collaborative file management in the Core science gateway architecture developed at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC). Our implementation is built on the Tapis Systems API, which provides endpoints that enable users to securely manage access to their research data.

Index Terms—science gateways, cyberinfrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

Science gateways empower researchers by providing a cohesive user interface for data management and job submission on HPC resources. The Web and Mobile Applications team at TACC maintains a Core science gateway platform which can be quickly deployed and customized to suit the needs of a research group or scientific organization [1]. In its default configuration, the Core science gateway provides a web frontend that gives users access to their data on TACC's HPC resources and the ability to submit jobs via SLURM. Interactions between the the Core gateway frontend and the HPC backend are mediated by Tapis, a cyberinfrastructure platform developed as a joint venture between TACC and the University of Hawaii [2]. Tapis provides RESTful API endpoints for data management and job submission. Tapis enables data management through its Systems API. A Tapis system represents a directory on a storage resource. Tapis exposes endpoints for managing access to that directory and for sharing access with other users. In the case where a system represents a POSIX filesystem, Tapis also includes endpoints for updating access control lists (ACLs) for files contained within the system.

In the Core science gateway architecture, collaborative file management is performed within a Shared Workspaces area in the web interface. Gateway users can create a new workspace at any time by providing a title and description. From a user's perspective, a Shared Workspace mostly behaves like any other directory that they have access to. Depending on their level of privilege users can list, preview, download, or rename files, as well as upload files from their personal computer or from other Tapis systems. The creator of a Shared Workspace has access to an administrative panel which allows additional members to be added to the workspace as either a "user" or "guest". The "user" role grants permissions for both read and write operations within the workspace directory, while the "guest" role is read-only. The workspace owner can modify other members' permissions at any time, or revoke a member's access entirely by removing them from the workspace.

II. IMPLEMENTATION OF SHARED WORKSPACES AS TAPIS SYSTEMS

The storage backend for Shared Workspaces is Corral, the high-performance storage resource maintained at TACC. Each gateway deployed using the Core architecture has a dedicated directory on Corral for workspace management. The root workspace directory is owned by a service user. The service user also owns a Tapis system pointed at this directory, so that the gateway backend can perform file operations within it by making calls to Tapis. When a researcher creates a new workspace through the web interface, the gateway backend calls the Tapis Files API with the service user's credential to create a new folder within the workspace root. A Tapis system is instantiated which points to the newly created folder. This system is owned by the researcher using the gateway, but it contains the service user's PKI credentials. This credential scheme allows users with permissions on the system to impersonate the service user when making Tapis calls, but only within a limited scope defined by the Tapis

TABLE I
MAPPING OF SHARED WORKSPACE OPERATIONS TO TAPIS CALLS

Workspace Operation	Tapis Implementation
Create a Shared Workspace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SERVICE CLIENT: mkdir in workspace root directory. • SERVICE CLIENT: setfacl d:u:\$USER_ID:rwX,u:\$USER_ID:rwX in workspace directory. • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): Create workspace system with the service user as effective user and title/description in Notes field. • USER CLIENT (project admin): Add service user's PKI key pair to the workspace system.
Add a new user to a Shared Workspace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): Share the system with the new user using the system sharing API. • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): Give user r(w)x permissions on the system root (Tapis files API) • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): setfacl d:u:\$USER_ID:r(w)X,u:\$USER_ID:r(w)X in workspace directory
Change the role of a workspace user	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): Give user r(w)x permissions on the system root (Tapis files API) • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): setfacl d:u:\$USER_ID:r(w)X,u:\$USER_ID:r(w)X in workspace directory
Remove a user from a workspace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): Delete permissions on system (Tapis systems API) and system root (Tapis files API) • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): Unshare the Tapis system with the specified user. • USER CLIENT (workspace owner): setfacl d:u:\$USER_ID:r(w)X,u:\$USER_ID:r(w)X in project directory
Update a workspace's title/description	USER CLIENT (project admin): Update title/description in the Notes field on the system.
List all Shared Workspaces accessible to a user	USER CLIENT (any valid Tapis client): Perform a system listing with a prefix query set to the gateway's unique workspace system prefix.

security kernel. Calls to the Tapis Files API that target this system cannot read or write files outside of the workspace's designated directory. The service user's PKI credential is never readable via Tapis.

When the workspace owner adds a new team member through the web interface, the Tapis System Sharing API is called to give that member "read" permissions on the system. This sharing mechanism causes the system to appear in listings performed using that user's Tapis client. Permissions are also set via the Files API as either read-only or read-write depending on the role assigned by the workspace owner. A user's role can be changed at any time by changing the permissions set via the Files API, or they can be removed by unsharing the system and deleting the associated file permissions. Table 1 contains a more thorough mapping of operations on Shared Workspaces to their respective Tapis calls, noting which calls require a service credential and which can be performed with a user's personal access token.

Because researchers can interact with Corral from outside of the Tapis ecosystem, their permissions on the physical file system should mirror their permissions in the Tapis security kernel. Each Tapis call that updates a user's file permissions is paired with a call to the ACL endpoint that applies the same permissions directly on Corral. This allows users to view and manage their files either through the gateway UI or through an

SSH session in Corral, while keeping permissions consistent. It permits data transfers into shared workspaces using established protocols such as Globus or SSHFS.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The abstractions and security model provided by the Tapis Systems API were instrumental in developing a collaborative data management feature for TACC's Core science gateway architecture. File sharing and role-based permission management were implemented entirely using idiomatic Tapis calls. With the ACL management endpoints exposed by the Tapis Files API, permissions could also be synchronized between the Tapis security kernel and the underlying POSIX file system on Corral.

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